

ISic2728

I.Sicily inscription 2728

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

Sporadic find in area of the agora

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG7542

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333215

1. [— — — — — — —]

2. [— —] Ἀππειραῖον.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645148

EDCS 64400335

PHI 333215

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Quarte

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